

**CLASSIFICATION OF GERMAN AND UZBEKIN PROVERBS AND
PHRASEOLOGICAL TERMS.**

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Abstract: Proverbs and proverbs are sources of emotional imagery of language. That is, proverbs are a people's advice, spiritual and moral conclusion, a reflection of the national spirit of the people. The proverb has a very deep social meaning. Therefore, some proverbs can illuminate the content of an entire work. This article is devoted to German phraseology, it talks about German phraseology and the problems of their transfer and translation into Uzbek.

Key words: phraseologisms, phraseology, German, artistic translation, problems, ways of translation.

"If I ask: can there be miracles in the language? If they ask, I would answer that the "miracle" of a language is its proverbs, sayings, and idioms. is important. But if the word of the fathers, which our people called "the eye of the mind", is compared with such expressions in other languages, it will be more meaningful if it is checked on the basis of examples of artistic translation. There are lexical and phraseological layers at the lexical level of language construction. The phraseological layer at the lexical level, as well as the field that studies it, is called phraseology. There is a broad understanding and a narrow understanding of the scope of phraseology. In a broad sense, phraseology, in addition to fixed combinations of words, also includes proverbs, proverbs, and aphorisms. Phraseology also includes understanding the semantic connections of words. Scientists, relying on specific scientific criteria, call phraseologisms, stable compounds or phraseological compounds (phrases) with a rather complex composition. The scientific study of phraseology is called phraseology.

It is known that in fiction, one or another events and evidences of reality related to the life of a certain nation are expressed in an artistically impressive form. The representation of images in the language, in particular, is carried out by means of phraseologisms, which have their own characteristics and especially the form of expression in each language. This is explained by the fact that phraseologisms with a large number of extralinguistic and ethnolinguistic factors have a more complex lexical-grammatical and semantic-syntactic construction. Such factors provide phraseologisms with a national character and play an important role in their formation and development. From this device, they more clearly show the people's thinking, the uniqueness of their culture, give the language a different national color and identity,

and enter the language system stably. In order to be a phraseology, a fixed combination of words must have a figurative meaning, a figurative meaning. The meaning understood as a whole from a phraseological unit is not equal to the simple sum of the lexical meanings of its components, the meaning of the phrase appears as a generalized meaning. To summarize our thoughts, when we say phraseologism, we understand language units or lexical units that are ready-made in the language and are brought into speech as such, similar in form to a phrase or sentence, and the content is based on figurative meaning. . In recent years, research in the field of phraseology is gaining special importance.

Phraseological dictionaries in different languages contain phraseology based on socio-historical evidence of social life, moral norms, attitudes to environmental phenomena, religious beliefs, national traditions and customs, and various genres of folk art. Such phraseologisms are considered specifically national, with the help of which the national coloring of the original is created. The national color of these phraseology is usually caused by the presence of components representing national realities in their composition. Analogous options that are similar in stylistic function and content, but differ in lexical content, cannot always replace each other. Interchangeability in translation is hindered by the presence of phraseologisms containing national realities. There are no analogues (equivalents) of some nationally specific phraseology. These are translated into another language using various techniques developed in translation experience. These methods have their positive and negative aspects. That's why the translation is a success. often depends on their appropriate and skillful use. It is impossible to acquire and use language wealth without a thorough study of the features and meaning of words. Phraseological units and stable word combinations are of great importance in increasing vocabulary. Phraseological units occupy an important place in the language, and the vocabulary level of language construction is made up of lexical and phraseological layers. Both the phraseological layer at the dictionary level and the field studying it are called phraseology. This field is a very complex linguistic process. Because from the emergence of phraseological units to the present day, the development of these units, changes and scientific works and researches of famous linguists conducted on them, keeping up with the news, expanding our scope of knowledge, thinking about phraseology in more detail. will teach.

Conclusion: Folk proverbs reflect the entire history of this nation, the way of life, so writers often refer to proverbs. Folk proverbs are an alternative methodical tool to make the language of an artistic work juicy and impressive. Figuratively speaking,

as an eye is an ornament to a ring, a proverb gives such power and vitality to the speaker's speech and the writer's image - proverbs given as epigraphs in some works serve to clearly express the idea and purpose of this work. Proverbs should be used appropriately, paying attention to who the speech or work is intended for, how it illuminates the idea, and the scope of influence. Concluding the above thoughts and comments, we can say the following. When using proverbs, it is necessary to pay special attention to their comprehensibility, correct use in their place, clear and effective speech.

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